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The Influence of the Level of Education on the Characteristics of the Experience of Interethnic Relations in Multinational Regions

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Abstract

In the situation of globalization processes and aggravation of interethnic relations in the modern world, the study of the influence of the level of education on interethnic interactions is relevant. We examined the problem of the relationship between education and interethnic relations using the example of the multinational region of the Middle East. As subjects, we studied Palestinians and Israelis.

The purpose of the study is to analyze the relationship between the characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of interethnic relations and the level of education of the subjects. The leading research method is the method of “perezhivanie” ‘experiencing’ of Fakhrutdinova (2008, 2009, 2010, 2012). The results showed that Palestinians and Israelis have a similar level of education, and the education factor does not affect the spatio-temporal and information-energy characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of interethnic relations. Significant differences were revealed in the energy, spatio-temporal characteristics of the “perezhivanie” ‘experiencing’ of interethnic relations. The results showed that the level of education does not affect the “perezhivanie” ‘experiencing’ of interethnic conflict, this scientific fact can have both applied value in the regulation of interethnic relations and theoretical significance in understanding the nature of interethnic conflicts.

Keywords: ethnic psychology, collective consciousness, collective experiences, interethnic relations, “perezhivanie”(experiencing), education.

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Introduction

The problem of interethnic relations in a multinational region is very relevant in the modern world. Especially, in its acute form - interethnic conflict. The theoretical basis for the subject approach in this work is the works of Russian scientists (Rubinstein, 1989; Brushlinsky, 2003; Znakov, 2005). We investigated the internal plan of interethnic relations - the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of interethnic conflict between Palestinians and Israelis. Proceedings of Vygotsky show that the internal, subjective plan of a social situation can be manifested through the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of a given situation (Vygotsky, 1987). We study the factor of subjects' education on human behavior in interethnic relations. We studied the subjective factor of interethnic relations on the basis of the theory of “perezhivanie” (experiencing) Fakhrutdinova (2008, 2009, 2010, 2012), in which the spatio-temporal and information-energetic, bodily, emotional and cognitive characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of a certain event are identified (Fakhrutdinova & Shawamri, 2018). The influence of the level of education of Palestinians and Israelis on the characteristics of the «perezhivanie» ‘experiencing’ of interethnic relations has been the subject of our research. The research problem is the insufficient study of the relationship between the characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of interethnic relations and the level of education of Palestinians and Israelis in the multinational region of the Middle East.

The experimental base of the study was the multinational region of the Middle East - Palestine and Israel. Subjects in the amount of 60 people (30 Palestinians and 30 Israelis) aged 18 to 30 years. The methodology for studying the structural organization of the experience of interethnic relations was “Questionnaire of “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of Fakhrutdinova, including the scales “Energy characteristics”, “Spatial characteristics”, “Time characteristics”, “Information characteristics” of “perezhivanie” (experiencing). Subjects (Palestinians and Israelis) were given a “Questionnaire of Experiences” as well as a questionnaire to identify educational levels.

The results showed that Palestinians and Israelis had a similar level of education, and the education factor did not affect the spatio-temporal and information-energy characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing). Significant differences were revealed in the energy, spatio-temporal characteristics of the

“perezhivanie” (experiencing). It was revealed that the energy and spatial characteristics are high among the representatives of both ethnic groups, and the temporal characteristics are low. Interethnic relations slow down time, impoverish the internal world of Palestinians and Israelis. Correlation analysis did not reveal reliable dependences of the level of education and characteristics of interethnic conflict. The level of education does not affect the subjective reality of the interethnic conflict of Palestinians and Israelis.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to study the relationship between the characteristics of the «perezhivanie» ‘experiencing’ of interethnic relations and the level of education of subjects.

1. To study the level of education of groups of Palestinians and Israelis.
2. To study the spatio-temporal and information-energy characteristics of the experience of the process of assimilation of knowledge in the educational activities of students.

Literature review

The cognitive component of experiencing a social conflict, especially at the escalation stage, is described in detail in Russian psychology, and the central belief that controls the course of conflict interaction is the belief in the incompatibility of the goals of the parties to the conflict (Bar-Tal, Kruglanski, & Klar, 1989). Another aspect of the cognitive component of experiencing conflict is the subjective assessment of the injustice of intergroup interaction (Merlin & Grishina, 1970; Deutsch, 1983). The cognitive component of difficult-to-resolve social conflicts includes the adequacy of awareness of the conditions that led to its occurrence (Deutsch, 2002; Petrovskaya, 2007), the perception of the enemy, the alien group and its members (Grishina, 2015; Lebedeva, 1999; Rubin, Pruit, & Kim, 2014; Stefanenko, 2004).

Boguslavsky (2000) defined collective experiences as the identity of the emotional states of people belonging to an emotional community, which narrows the idea of the structure of experience in accordance with our concept of the structural-dynamic organization of experience.

The “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of intractable conflicts is actively studied in Western psychology, in the context of which collective emotional experiences are of paramount, dominant importance, often determining the scenario of events (Stefanenko, 2004; Halperin, Sharvit, & Gross, 2011; Barbalet, 1999). The most studied emotions are fear (for example, before future humiliation), anger (for the deliberate nature of pain and suffering inflicted). A model of collective emotions based on cognitive assessment was

proposed on the example of relations between Palestinians and Israelis during the last episode of the war in the Gaza Strip (Halperin, Sharvit, & Gross; Fakhrutdinova & Shawamri, 2018).

Länge (2007) pointed out that in psychology, experience occupies a central place, and represents the “intersection point” (“point of contact”) of the inner and outer world. R.D. Laing is the fundamental principle, the very existence of the inner world, the "Soul of man" of his experience. Human behavior, in his opinion, is a “function of experience”. A holistic view of human nature is required for psychological research. When studying it, it is necessary to investigate both the experiences and the behavior of the individual (Laing, 1990). Shpet first introduced the concept of "collective experiences", which expresses the attitude of the people and their representatives to various cultural phenomena, thus, the experience is defined as the unity of personality and culture. Cultural products evoke typical experiences among the representatives of the people (1989). Thus, Shpet urged to study not so much the products of culture as the experience of cultural values by representatives of a given nation. The problem of experiencing educational activity is considered in the articles of Fakhrutdinova and Sabirov (2017). Research has shown that the structure of experiencing the learning activity of schoolchildren differs depending on the cultural and historical context.

Methodology

The experimental base of the study was the multinational region of the Middle East - Palestine and Israel. Subjects in the amount of 60 people (30 Palestinians and 30 Israelis) aged 18 to 30 years.

The methodology for studying the structural organization of the experience of interethnic relations - “Questionnaire of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) (Fakhrutdinova, 2012) including the scales “Energy characteristics”, “Spatial characteristics”, “Time characteristics”, “Information characteristics” of “perezhivanie” (experiencing). Also, an author's questionnaire to identify the level of education.

The “Questionnaire of Experiences” measures spatial, temporal, energy, and informational characteristics. (Fakhrutdinova, 2012). The “Temporal characteristic” scale means how the process of «perezhivanie» ‘experiencing’ affects the course of internal time. High values show that this “perezhivanie” (experiencing) causes a subjective feeling of speeding up time, saturating it with events. Low values mean that the experienced events cause a feeling of time dilation, its ductility and painfully slow flow. The scale “Energy characteristic” reflects the intensity, strength, brightness, power of the subject’s “perezhivanie” (experiencing). High rates on this scale indicate that the subject experiences very intense, energetically charged experiences. Low indicators reflect sluggish experiences of very low intensity. The scale "Spatial characteristic" shows the volume, breadth and depth of «perezhivanie» ‘experiencing’ of the inner life of a

person. High values a high level of "capture" of this experience. Low values indicate a low degree of inner world engagement with these experiences. The scale "Information characteristic" shows the significance of this "perezhivanie" (experiencing) for the subject. High rates reflect the high importance of the "perezhivanie" (experiencing) for the subject. Low indicators mean that this experience is insignificant for the subject.

Research procedure. Subjects (Palestinians and Israelis) were given a "Questionnaire of Experiences" as well as a questionnaire to identify educational levels. The data obtained were subjected to qualitative and quantitative analysis.

Results

The results of inductive statistics (comparison of average values) of a questionnaire to identify the level of education of Palestinians and Israelis showed that no significant differences were found for this indicator. The education level of Palestinians and Israelis is not different in this study.

Figure 1 shows the spatio-temporal and information-energy characteristics of the «perezhivanie» 'experiencing' of interethnic conflict by Palestinians and Israelis.

Figure 1. Average values of spatio-temporal and information-energy characteristics of the «perezhivanie» 'experiencing' of interethnic relations between Palestinians and Israelis

Legend: 1 - indicators of the scale “Energy characteristic”, 2 - indicators of the scale “Spatial characteristic”, 3 - indicators of the scale “Time characteristic”, 4 - indicators of the scale “Information characteristic” of the “Questionnaire of experience”. Row 1 corresponds to the values of the characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of interethnic relations of the Palestinians, row 2 - corresponds to the values of the characteristics of the «perezhivanie» ‘experiencing’ of interethnic relations of the Israelis.

Inductive statistics have shown the reliability of differences in energy, spatial and temporal characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of interethnic relations between Palestinians and Israelis. The results indicate that the subjective reality of the interethnic conflict of Palestinians and Israelis is significantly different. Figure 1 shows that the energy ($F = 7.317$, at $p = 0.009$) and spatial ($F = 5.043$, at $p = 0.029$) characteristics of the experience of interethnic relations of Israelis are significantly higher than that of Palestinians, that is, Israelis experience these interethnic relations more strongly and deeper. At the same time, it is necessary to note the high energy level of experiencing interethnic conflict among representatives of both peoples. The time parameters of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing) of the Palestinians and Israelis are slowed down, which means the slowdown of the subjective time of the Palestinians and Israelis in connection with this conflict. These interethnic relations are painful for both sides of the conflict. In Israel, the time dilation was significantly more pronounced ($F = 9.56$, at $p = 0.003$). The informational characteristics of both sides of the interethnic conflict are of high importance, which means that these relations change the representatives of both ethnic groups. Moreover, the difference between them is not reliable, which shows the unity of the process of change affecting the Palestinian and Israeli peoples during the inter-ethnic conflict.

Correlation analysis did not reveal reliable dependences of the level of education and characteristics of interethnic conflict. The level of education does not affect the subjective reality of the interethnic conflict of Palestinians and Israelis.

Discussions

This work is devoted to the study of the relationship between the level of education and characteristics of the experience of interethnic conflict between Palestinians and Israelis. The educational level of the Palestinians and Israelis was examined. In general, the level of education is above average. Also, the space-time and information-energy characteristics of the experience of interethnic conflict were studied.

Revealed significant differences in the energy, time, spatial component of the experience of interethnic relations between Palestinians and Israelis. It was revealed that representatives of both ethnic groups experience the conflict strongly, deeply, that this conflict has a noticeable meaning in their life, changes

their subjective reality. But the influence of the level of education on these changes, measured by the spatio-temporal and informational-energy components of the experience of interethnic conflict, was not revealed. Research on the bodily and emotional components of the experience has shown a more complex nature of the response to interethnic conflict (Fakhrutdinova & Shawamri, 2018).

The structural organization of the experience showed the dependence of the spatio-temporal and informational-energy characteristics of experiencing a social situation depending on ethnicity using the example of Russians and Chinese (Fakhrutdinova & Sabirov, 2017). Further research is needed on the impact of education on interethnic relations in multinational regions.

Conclusion

The research problem is the insufficient knowledge of the relationship of the spatio-temporal and information-energy characteristics of the “perezhivanie” ‘experiencing’ of interethnic relations in a multinational region and the level of education of subjects of interethnic relations. The results showed that Palestinians and Israelis have a similar level of education, and the education factor does not affect the spatio-temporal and information-energy characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing). Significant differences were revealed in the energy, spatio-temporal characteristics of the “perezhivanie” (experiencing). It was revealed that the energy and spatial characteristics are high among representatives of both ethnic groups, and the temporal characteristics are low. Interethnic relations slow down subjective time, impoverish the number of events in the inner world of the Palestinians and Israelis.

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